

Competitive inhibitor-mediated gasocrine signaling

Savani Anbalagan^{1,2}

¹Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Biology, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Poznań, Poland.

²Correspondence

E-mail: savani.anbalagan@amu.edu.pl

Tel: +48 61 829 5905

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To investigate gasocrine signaling, it is essential to identify all the gas-sensing polymeric molecules. I have recently proposed the term gasoreceptor protein to unify all proteins that can bind and sense gaseous molecules *per se*. Examples of oxygen (O₂)-sensing gasoreceptors include *E. coli* Dos phosphodiesterase, *R. meliloti* FixI kinase and soluble adenylate and guanylate cyclases in *L. major* and *C. elegans*, respectively. During the origins of gasocrine signaling, it is unclear whether sensing of gaseous molecules/solutes occurred via a single domain or two or more domains/regions. I hypothesize that evolutionarily ancient gasoreceptor proteins used a single domain/region to sense gaseous molecules (or perhaps even other classes of molecules that can compete with gas-binding sites). Since some of the gaseous molecules can competitively inhibit enzyme activity, a debate is warranted as to whether all such competitively inhibiting gaseous molecules and enzymes are ligands (in terms of ligand-receptor-mediated signaling) and gas-sensing gasoreceptor proteins, respectively. Acceptance of gaseous molecule-based competitive inhibitors as ligands will allow the inclusion of all metalloenzymes and metalloribozymes as *potential* gas-sensing gasoreceptors and gasoriboceptors, respectively, mediating gasocrine signaling.